

PROBLEMS OF INTERNATIONAL REGULATION OF INFORMATION SECURITY

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Annotation. Cyber activities have become an integral part of international relations. The vast interconnectedness of networks, technologies and cyber processes across borders has brought societies and individuals from different nations closer together and has opened up new opportunities for cooperation among both State and non-State actors. At the same time, States and societies have grown highly dependent on the functioning of infrastructures. The aim of this article is to clarify the problems of international regulations on information security.

Key words: Information technology IT, information security, International law, cyber activity, cybercrime, International regulation.

Introduction

IT has created new vulnerabilities. In cyberspace, only limited resources are often needed to cause significant harm. This poses security threats for States and societies. Harmful cross-border cyber operations, both by State and non-State actors, can jeopardize international stability.

Germany is firmly convinced that international law is of critical importance when dealing with opportunities and risks related to the use of information and communication technologies in the international context. As a main pillar of a rules-based international order, international law as it stands provides binding

guidance on States' use and regulation of information and communication technologies and their defence against malicious cyber operations. In particular, the UN Charter fulfils a core function with regard to the maintenance of international peace and security – also in relation to cyber activities. In this regard, Germany reemphasizes its conviction that international law, including the UN Charter and international humanitarian law (IHL), applies without reservation in the context of cyberspace.¹

Methodology

This article discusses selected aspects of the interpretation of certain core principles and rules of international law in the cyber context.² Germany thereby aims to contribute to the ongoing discussion on the modalities of application of international law – most of which predates the development and rise of information and communication technologies – in the cyber context. The paper also intends to foster transparency, comprehensibility and legal certainty with regard to an important aspect of foreign affairs. The explanations take into account, inter alia, the 2013 and 2015 reports of the United Nations Group of Governmental Experts on Developments in the Field of Information and Telecommunications in the Context of International Security.¹ They are based on applicable international law and in this regard consider, to a significant degree, the findings of independent international law experts recorded in the Tallinn Manual 2.0.²

Data collection and Analysis

'Cyber processes' are events and sequences of events of data creation, storage,

¹ See above, note 1.

² Schmitt, M. (gen. ed.)/Vihul, L. (man. ed.), Tallinn Manual 2.0 on the International Law Applicable to Cyber

Operations, Prepared by the International Groups of Experts at the Invitation of the NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence, 2nd edition, Cambridge University Press 2017. The Tallinn Manual 2.0 is a paper created by independent experts and constitutes neither a document stating NATO positions nor a position paper by States. In the following, references to the Tallinn Manual 2.0 are made for information purposes only and do not necessarily constitute an endorsement of the referenced text by the German government.

processing, alteration or relocation through means of information technology. The term ‘cyber infrastructure’ refers to all types of hardware and software components, systems and networks which allow for the implementation of ‘cyber processes’. This includes ‘[t]he communications, storage, and computing devices upon which information systems are built and operate.’³ ‘Cyber activities’ are ‘cyber processes’ instigated by users of cyber infrastructure. The term ‘cyber operation’ more narrowly refers to the ‘employment of cyber capabilities to achieve objectives in or through cyberspace.’⁴ ‘Cyberspace’ itself is understood here as the conglomerate of (at least partly interconnected) ‘cyber infrastructures’ and ‘cyber processes’ in the above-mentioned sense. In this paper, the adjective ‘malicious’, when used to describe certain activities in cyberspace, is not purported to carry a technical legal meaning.

The legal principle of State sovereignty⁵ applies to States’ activities with regard to cyberspace.⁶ State sovereignty implies, inter alia, that a State retains a right of regulation, enforcement and adjudication (jurisdiction) with regard to both persons engaging in cyber activities and cyber infrastructure on its territory.⁷ It is limited only by relevant rules of international law, including international humanitarian law and international human rights law. Germany recognizes that due to the high degree of cross-border interconnectedness of cyber infrastructures, a State’s exercise of its jurisdiction may have unavoidable and immediate repercussions for the cyber infrastructure of other States.⁸ While this does not

³ Tallinn Manual 2.0 (note 4), Glossary (p. 564).

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ The legal principle of State sovereignty is enshrined – in conjunction with the notion of equality of States – in Art. 2 para. 1 of the UN Charter.

⁶ See also UN Group of Governmental Experts, reports of 2013 and 2015 (note 1), paras. 20 and 27, 28 (b) respectively; Tallinn Manual 2.0 (note 4), rule 1.

⁷ A State’s jurisdiction may under certain conditions apply to situations beyond its borders, i.e. according to the principles of active and of passive nationality as well as universality.

⁸ For example, restrictive regulatory or enforcement activities regarding important internet nodes in the territory of one State

limit a State's right to exercise its jurisdiction, due regard has to be given to potential adverse effects on third States.

By virtue of sovereignty, a State's political independence is protected and it retains the right to freely choose its political, social, economic and cultural system. Inter alia, a State may generally decide freely which role information and communication technologies should play in its governmental, administrative and adjudicative proceedings. Foreign interference in the conduct of elections of a State may under certain circumstances constitute a breach of sovereignty or, if pursued by means of coercion, of the prohibition of wrongful intervention.⁹ Moreover, by virtue of its sovereignty, a State may decide freely over its foreign policy also in the field of information and communication technologies.¹⁰

Furthermore, a State's territorial sovereignty is protected. Due to the rootedness of all cyber activities in the actions of human beings using physical infrastructure, cyberspace is not a deterritorialized forum.¹¹ In this regard, Germany underlines that there are no independent 'cyber borders' incongruent with a State's physical borders which would limit or disregard the territorial scope of its sovereignty. Within its borders, a State has the exclusive right – within the framework of international law – to fully exercise its authority, which includes the protection of cyber activities, persons engaging therein as well as cyber infrastructures in the territory of a State against cyber and non-cyber-related interferences attributable to foreign States.¹²

As a corollary to the rights conferred on States by the rule of territorial sovereignty, States are under an 'obligation not to allow knowingly their territory

may seriously impair the functioning of networks of other States.

⁹ See below, at II.b).

¹⁰ See Tallinn Manual 2.0 (note 4), rule 3 ('external sovereignty').

¹¹ *Ibid.*, rule 1, commentary, para. 5.

¹² *Ibid.*, rule 2 with commentary, para. 2.

to be used for acts contrary to the rights of other States'¹³ – this generally applies to such use by State and non-State actors. The ‘due diligence principle’, which is widely recognized in international law, is applicable to the cyber context as well and gains particular relevance here because of the vast interconnectedness of cyber systems and infrastructures.

Germany agrees with the view that cyber operations attributable to States which violate the sovereignty of another State are contrary to international law.¹⁶ In this regard, State sovereignty constitutes a legal norm in its own right and may apply directly as a general norm also in cases in which more specific rules applicable to State behaviour, such as the prohibition of intervention or the use of force, are not applicable. Violations of State sovereignty may *inter alia* involve its territorial dimension; in this regard, the following categories of cases may be relevant (without excluding the possibility of other cases):

Germany essentially concurs with the view proffered, *inter alia*, in the Tallinn Manual 2.0 that cyber operations attributable to a State which lead to physical effects and harm in the territory of another State constitute a violation of that State’s territorial sovereignty.¹⁴ This encompasses physical damage to cyber infrastructure components *per se* and physical effects of such damage on persons or on other infrastructure, *i.e.* cyber or analogue infrastructure components connected to the damaged cyber component or infrastructure located in the vicinity of the damaged cyber infrastructure (provided a sufficient causal link can be established).

Germany generally also concurs with the view expressed and discussed in the Tallinn Manual 2.0 that certain effects in form of functional impairments with

¹³ See International Court of Justice (ICJ), *Corfu Channel case (United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland v. Albania)*, Judgement of 9 April 1949, I.C.J. Reports 1949, 4, 22; Permanent Court of Arbitration (PCA - administering institution), *Island of Palmas Case (or Miangas), United States of America v. The Netherlands*, Arbitral Award (M. Huber) of 4 April 1928, (1928) II RIAA 829, 839. ¹⁶ Cf. Tallinn Manual 2.0 (note 4), rule 4.

¹⁴ Tallinn Manual 2.0 (note 4), rule 4, commentary, para. 11.

regard to cyber infrastructures located in a State's territory may constitute a violation of a State's territorial sovereignty.¹⁵ In Germany's view, this may also apply to certain substantial non-physical (i.e. software-related) functional impairments. In such situations, an evaluation of all relevant circumstances of the individual case will be necessary. If functional impairments result in substantive secondary or indirect physical effects in the territory of the target State (and a sufficient causal link to the cyber operation can be established), a violation of territorial sovereignty will appear highly probable.¹⁶

In any case, negligible physical effects and functional impairments below a certain impact threshold cannot – taken by themselves – be deemed to constitute a violation of territorial sovereignty.

Generally, the fact that a piece of critical infrastructure (i.e. infrastructure which plays an indispensable role in ensuring the functioning of the State and its society) or a company of special public interest in the territory of a State has been affected may indicate that a State's territorial sovereignty has been violated. However, this cannot in and of itself constitute a violation, inter alia because uniform international definitions of the terms do not yet exist. Also, cyber operations in which infrastructures and/or companies which do not qualify as 'critical' or 'of particular public interest' are affected may likewise violate the territorial sovereignty of a State.

The prohibition of a wrongful intervention between States¹⁷ is not explicitly mentioned in the UN Charter. However, it is a corollary of the sovereignty principle, can be derived from art. 2 para. 1 UN Charter and is grounded in customary international law. Generally, for Stateattributable conduct to qualify as

¹⁵ Cf. *ibid.*, rule 4, commentary, para. 13 ("loss of functionality").

¹⁶ Cf. *ibid.*

¹⁷ On its applicability in the cyber context see also UN Group of Governmental Experts, report of 2015 (note 1), para. 28 (b).

a wrongful intervention, the conduct must ¹⁸(1) interfere with the *domaine réservé* of a foreign State and (2) involve coercion.²¹ Especially the definition of the latter element requires further clarification in the cyber context.

In its Nicaragua judgement, the International Court of Justice (ICJ) held that ‘[t]he element of coercion, which defines, and indeed forms the very essence of, prohibited intervention, is particularly obvious in the case of an intervention which uses force, either in the direct form of military action, or in the indirect form of support for subversive or terrorist armed activities within another State.’¹⁹

Malicious cyber activities will only in some cases amount to direct or indirect use of force.²⁰ However, measures below this threshold may also qualify as coercive. Generally, Germany is of the opinion that cyber measures may constitute a prohibited intervention under international law if they are comparable in scale and effect to coercion in non-cyber contexts.

Coercion implies that a State’s internal processes regarding aspects pertaining to its *domaine réservé* are significantly influenced or thwarted and that its will is manifestly bent by the foreign State’s conduct. However, as is widely accepted, the element of coercion must not be assumed prematurely. Even harsher forms of communication such as pointed commentary and sharp criticism as well as (persistent) attempts to obtain, through discussion, a certain reaction or the performance of a certain measure from another State do not as such qualify as coercion. Moreover, the acting State must intend to intervene in the internal affairs of the target State²¹ – otherwise the scope of the non-intervention principle would be unduly broad.

¹⁸ International Court of Justice (ICJ), *Military and Paramilitary Activities in and against Nicaragua (Nicaragua v. United States of America)*, Merits, Judgement of 27 June 1986, I.C.J. Reports 1986, 14, para. 205.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*

²⁰ See below, at II.c).

²¹ Cf. Tallinn Manual 2.0 (note 4), rule 66, commentary, para. 27. ²⁵ See also above, II.a).

In the context of wrongful intervention, the problem of foreign electoral interference by means of malicious cyber activities has become particularly virulent. Germany generally agrees with the opinion that malicious cyber activities targeting foreign elections may – either individually or as part of a wider campaign involving cyber and non-cyber-related tactics – constitute a wrongful intervention.²⁵ For example, it is conceivable that a State, by spreading disinformation via the internet, may deliberately incite violent political upheaval, riots and/or civil strife in a foreign country, thereby significantly impeding the orderly conduct of an election and the casting of ballots. Such activities may be comparable in scale and effect to the support of insurgents and may hence be akin to coercion in the above-mentioned sense. A detailed assessment of the individual case would be necessary.

Also, the disabling of election infrastructure and technology such as electronic ballots, etc. by malicious cyber activities may constitute a prohibited intervention, in particular if this compromises or even prevents the holding of an election, or if the results of an election are thereby substantially modified.

Furthermore, beyond the mentioned examples, cyber activities targeting elections may be comparable in scale and effect to coercion if they aim at and result in a substantive disturbance or even permanent change of the political system of the targeted State, i.e. by significantly eroding public trust in a State's political organs and processes, by seriously impeding important State organs in the fulfilment of their functions or by dissuading significant groups of citizens from voting, thereby undermining the meaningfulness of an election. Due to the complexity and singularity of such scenarios, it is difficult to formulate abstract criteria. Discussions in this context are still ongoing.

The ICJ has stated in its Nuclear Weapons opinion that Charter provisions 'apply

to any use of force, regardless of the weapons employed.’²² Germany shares the view that with regard to the definition of ‘use of force’, emphasis needs to be put on the effects rather than on the means used.

Cyber operations can cross the threshold into use of force and cause significant damage in two ways. Firstly, they can be part of a wider kinetic attack. In such cases they are one component of a wider operation clearly involving the use of physical force, and can be assessed within the examination of the wider incident. Secondly, outside the wider context of a kinetic military operation, cyber operations can by themselves cause serious harm and may result in massive casualties.

The determination of a cyber operation as having crossed the threshold of a prohibited use of force is a decision to be taken on a case-by-case basis. Based on the assessment of the scale and effects of the operation, the broader context of the situation and the significance of the malicious cyber operation will have to be taken into account. Qualitative criteria which may play a role in the assessment are, inter alia, the severity of the interference, the immediacy of its effects, the degree of intrusion into a foreign cyber infrastructure and the degree of organization and coordination of the malicious cyber operation.

Result and Discussion

An international armed conflict – a main prerequisite for the applicability of IHL in a concrete case – is characterized by armed hostilities between States. This may also encompass hostilities that are partially or totally conducted by using cyber means. Germany holds the view that cyber operations of a non-international character, e.g. of armed groups against a State, which reach a sufficient extent, duration, or intensity (as opposed to acts of limited impact) may be considered a non-international armed conflict and thereby also trigger the application of IHL.³⁰

²² International Court of Justice (ICJ), Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons, Advisory Opinion of 8 July 1996, I.C.J. Reports 1996, 226, para. 39.

At the same time, cyber actions can become part of an ongoing armed conflict. In order to fall within the ambit of IHL, the cyber operation must show a sufficient nexus with the armed conflict,³¹ i.e. the cyber operation must be conducted by a party to the conflict against its opponent and must contribute to its military effort.³²

Cyber operations between a non-State actor and a State alone may provoke a noninternational armed conflict. However, this will only seldom be the case due to the level of intensity, impact and extent of hostilities required. Thus, activities such as a large-scale intrusion into foreign cyber systems, significant data theft, the blocking of internet services and the defacing of governmental channels or websites will usually not singularly and in themselves bring about a non-international armed conflict.³³

The basic principles governing the conduct of hostilities, including by cyber means, such as the principles of distinction, proportionality, precautions in attack and the prohibition of unnecessary suffering and superfluous injury, apply to cyber attacks in international as well ²³as in non-international armed conflicts.

Germany defines a cyber attack in the context of IHL as an act or action initiated in or through cyberspace to cause harmful effects on communication, information or other electronic systems, on the information that is stored, processed or transmitted on these systems or on physical objects or persons.³⁴ The occurrence of physical damage, injury or death to persons or damage or destruction to objects comparable to effects of conventional weapons is not required for an attack in the sense of art. 49 para. 1 Additional Protocol I to the Geneva Conventions.²⁴ However, the mere intrusion into foreign networks and the copying of data does not constitute an attack under IHL.

²³ See also NATO Terminology Tracking Form (TTF) 2015-0028 (last entry 2019-02-12).

²⁴ Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Protocol I), 8 June 1977, 1125 UNTS 3.

The principle of distinction obliges States to differentiate between military and civilian objects, as well as between civilians, on the one hand, and combatants, members of organized armed groups and civilians taking direct part in hostilities, on the other hand. While IHL does not prohibit an attack on the latter, civilians (not taking direct part in hostilities) and civilian objects must be spared.

Civilians operating in cyberspace can be considered as taking direct part in hostilities with the result of losing their protection from attack and the effects of the hostilities, provided the following conditions are met: Their acts are likely to adversely affect the military operations or military capacity of a party, there is a direct causal link between their acts and the adverse effects and the acts are specifically designed to inflict harm in support of a party to an armed conflict and to the detriment of another (belligerent nexus).²⁵ Thus, Germany agrees with the view that, for example, ‘electronic interference with military computer networks, whether through computer network attacks or computer network exploitation, as well as wiretapping adversary’s high command or transmitting tactical targeting information for an attack’, could suffice in order to consider a civilian person as directly participating in hostilities.²⁶

Conclusion

In general, a civilian object like a computer, computer networks, and cyber infrastructure, or even data stocks, can become a military target, if used either for both civilian and military purposes or exclusively for the latter. However, in cases of doubt, the determination that a civilian computer is in fact used to make an effective contribution to military action may only be made after a careful assessment. Should substantive doubts remain as to the military use of the object under consideration, it shall be presumed not to be so used.

²⁵ International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC)/Melzer, N., Interpretive guidance on the notion of direct participation in hostilities under international humanitarian law, 2009, available at www.icrc.org, p. 16.

²⁶ *ibid.*, p. 48 (footnotes omitted).

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UN Group of Governmental Experts, reports of 2013 and 2015 (note 1), paras. 20 and 27, 28 (b) respectively; Tallinn Manual 2.0 (note 4), rule 1